

TRIBALS ARE THE BACKBONE OF INDIA: HEAD AND HEART

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Abstract

India has always been renowned for its artwork and buildings. India has a long and rich artistic history and this artistic art comes from the tribal people it's very interesting to know that tribals are playing a very important role in the Indian economy hence tribals are the pillars of the culture. In India, Almost every state has a particular art form with a niche. And the most vivid art comes from Indian tribal cultures. Due to the highly specialized rites and qualities of these tribal arts, they were rich in symbolic elements. The people of India and other nations are changing their perceptions of tribal people and their products, whether they come from forestry, handlooms, jewelry, fabrics, etc. since we are fast developing day by day. Here, the researcher attempts to learn more about the tribes, and after examining a variety of reviews of literature, the researcher discovers that tribes now are the new age leaders who create new markets around the world. Let's discuss more this indigenous art, numerous studies have been done on tribals, but less attention has been paid to determining the process by which tribal leaders emerge. Here, the Government plays a major role in establishing them as innovators and creative leaders. We reside in a democracy where everyone is entitled to certain freedoms. Since we know everything about tribal people, we sometimes treat them with empathy and compassion. As a result, tribal people have been leaders since ancient times since they are renowned as artisans. Therefore, the researchers' primary concern is to address the many Government programs for tribal people that allow them to easily build their reputation in the modern world. Here, the researcher uses secondary data to illustrate how tribal people merge into the new contemporary society.

Keywords: Tribal, Marketing, Handicraft, Agriculture, Artisans, Art Market, Development, Training, Online Platform, Compassion, Empathy

According to the Imperial Gazetteer,

“A tribe is a collection of families bearing a common name speaking a common dialect, occupying or professing to occupy a common territory and is not usually endogamous though originally it might have been so.”

Introduction

The Middle English word tribu, which ultimately derives from the Latin word tribus, is the source of the current English word tribe. The Oxford English Dictionary states that it is still unknown whether this form was directly borrowed from Latin or if it was derived from a Romance language source (such as Old French tribu). Middle

English plural *tribuz* 1250 may be a direct translation of Latin plural *tribs*. The straight Latinization of English nouns without the addition of suffixes, such as *-us*, may also have contributed to the development of the modern English *tribe*. Linguists generally agree that the Latin word *tribus* is a combination of the two parts *tri-*, which means "three," and *bhu, bu, fu*, which is a verbal root that means "to be."

The Scheduled Tribes are those tribes, tribal communities, parts of these tribes, and tribal communities, or groups within these tribes and tribal communities that have been declared as such by the President by a public announcement, according to Article 342 of the Constitution. Many tribal tribes have adapted to modern life, however, some tribal groups are more vulnerable than others. Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs) were given their category by the Dhebar Commission in 1973. Their susceptibility results from their substantial culture and varied livelihood practices rather than from their primitive life and exclusion from current social norms. They are crucial to maintaining India's diversity, which is a strength of ours and a symbol of our "Unity in Diversity" around the world.

A tribe is described as a collection of indigenous people who share a common name, a common language, a shared territory, and strong kinship ties. They also practice endogamy and have unique customs, rituals, and beliefs, among other things. Such definitions are not particularly helpful because different tribes' lifestyles vary greatly.

In India, there are numerous tribes, dispersed throughout various regions and with varying levels of socioeconomic development. According to S. C. Sinha, the ideal definition of a tribe is one in which it is cut off from the networks of social connections and cultural exchanges that exist in the centers of civilization. Sinha asserts that "despite their isolation, tribal societies are sustained by relatively adolescent subsistence technologies such as shifting farming and, hunting and gathering and preserve an egalitarian segmentary social framework governed by traditional tribal customs" exclusively by illiterate ethnic tradition. "Mobility and change" have an impact on the tribes in India. There are many instances of tribes assimilating into the greater caste structure; some tribes have converted to Christianity or Islam. Additionally, they become members of the peasantry, and in more recent periods, they work as wage laborers in factories, plantations, and mines. Therefore, it is important to consider migration and change while considering tribes.

A new wave of constitutional planning for affirmative action has emerged in postwar India as a result of the colonial Indian state's inability to institutionalize, intervene in, and control development policy for the benefit of people in general and tribals in particular. This phase has mostly been linked to the transition from colonial control to the nationalistic ethos expressed in the Indian freedom fight, giving significance to the state for welfare programs with a special focus on the development of the tribals. Though aiming at tribal development, more than six decades of Indian independence and planning for development have failed to meet the fundamental developmental objectives. It shows that the postcolonial Indian state has mostly failed to institutionalize, act in, and regulate. The goal of development policy is to improve the welfare of the underprivileged, or the indigenous people. In such a setting, the process of "integration and assimilation" approach towards the tribal development policy of the postcolonial Indian state undermines the currency of the so-called transformative vocabulary, such as "development," "empowerment," "participation," or "capacity building." Additionally, the introduction of new economic policies (liberalization, privatization, and globalization) made tribal development policy more vulnerable by transferring power from the state to the market rather than the poor. In the end, the state's welfare schemes and weakened enforcement prevented tribe growth indirectly. Therefore, a policy for tribal development as well as alternative political leverage is required for the tribes to have an adequate development policy and practice. This section aims to Talk about the history of India's tribal peoples being denied development under the tribal development policy. The exploration of tribal development in India in this chapter also aims to challenge the notion of "social capital." The main cause of the underdevelopment of tribals and their region, according to current policymakers for tribal development in India, is the underutilization of social capital. It appears to be one of the ways the Indian state's institutional obligation is shifted to its historically disadvantaged population, the tribals. In addition to presenting the paradigm of development policy for tribal people, the chapter also seeks to challenge the bureaucratic and apolitical responses to tribal underdevelopment.

Theoretically or practically, anthropologists, sociologists, social workers, policymakers, administrators, and others have occasionally been associated with tribes and their problems. A tribe is described as "a collection of families or group of families bearing a common name, occupying the same territory, speaking the same language, and observing certain taboos regarding marriage, profession, or occupation and having developed a well-assessed system of reciprocity and mutuality of obligations." This definition was provided by Majumdar in 1961. A tribe

is a social unit that has reached a low or barbaric stage of development. The tribes of India have the following characteristics, according to T. B. Naik (1968).

The tribe should have the least amount of reliance that is useful. within a neighborhood.

- 1) It ought to have a poor economy.
- 2) The population should be relatively isolated from other areas geographically. Members of a tribe should speak a similar dialect that may vary depending on the locale.
- 3) The tribe should have customary rules, and its members may suffer in court as a result of these laws.
- 4) The tribe should be politically organized, and its community Panchayat should be a powerful organization.

The Tribes are commonly referred to as Adivasis. In this nation, Adivasis are considered the poorest of the poor. Although they may have had a lovely past, their current situation is terrible. They rely on the trees for their livelihood and live in hilly and forested locations. On the one hand, they lead normal lives, but on the other, they are excluded from the mainstream of contemporary Indian progress. Tribal people's lives are dominated by complicated issues like illiteracy, land alienation, exploitation, poverty, and lack of information. They have limited access to jobs, easy finance, market technologies, and information. They also have limited access to education, health, and nutrition. Even though the position of Adivasis varies widely depending on their socioeconomic and ethnic backgrounds, women nevertheless experience discrimination in many facets of life within this social group.

State-wise Schedule Tribe distribution

There are more than 705 Indian tribes that have lived in the nation for a very long time.

Every community is unique in some way that sets it apart from the other tribes.

One thing unites all of these communities: they are cut off from the outside world.

They are content with their choice despite not being informed of global technological and social advancements.

State-wise population chart

States	Major Tribes	No. of Tribes	PTGs
North East			
Mizoram	Lusai, Kuki, Garo, Khasi, Jayantia, Mikir etc.	15	NA
Nagaland	Naga, Kuki, Mikir, Garo, etc.	05	NA
Meghalaya	Garo, Khasi, Jayantia, etc.	17	NA
Sikkim	Lepcha, Bhutia, Limbu, and Tamang	4	NA
Tripura	Chakma, Garo, Khasi, Kuki, Lusai, Liang, Santhal etc	19	01
Arunachal Pr	Dafla, Khampti, Singpho etc.	16	NA
Assam	Boro, Kachari, Mikir (Karbi), Lalung, Hajong etc	15	NA
Manipur	Meities, Pangals, Naga tribes, Kuki etc.	33	01
East			
Orissa	Birhor, Gond, Juang, Khond, Korua, Oraon, Tharua,	62	13
West Bengal	Asur, Birhor, Korwa, Lepcha, Munda, Santhal, etc.	40	03
Bihar	Asur, Banjara, Birhor, Korwa, Oraon, Santhal, etc.	33	09
Jharkhand	Biga, Banjara, Bathudi, Bedia, Bhumij, Chik, Baraik, etc	30	
Central			
Madhya Pradesh	Bhil, Birhor, Damar, Gond, Kharia, Oraon, Parahi, etc.	21	03
Chhattisgarh	Gond, Baiga, Korba, Bison Horn Maria, Halba etc.	31	04
West			
Gujarat	Bhil, Dhodia, Gond, Siddi, Bordia, etc.	31	05
Rajasthan	Bhil, Damor, Garasia, Meena, Sahariya etc.	12	01
Maharashtra	Bhil, Bhunjia, Chodhara, Dhodia, Nayaka, Rathwa etc.	48	03
Goa	Dhodi, and Siddi (Nayaka).	08	NA
Daman & Diu	Dubla, Dhodia, Varli, Naikda & Siddi	5	NA
Dadra&Nagar	Dhodia, Dubla, Kathodi, Kokna, Koli, Dhor, and Varli	7	NA
North			
UP & Uttaranchal	Bhoti, Buxa, Jaunsari, Tharu, and Raji	15	2
Himachal Pradesh	Gaddi, Gujjar, Lahuala, Swangla, etc.	10	NA
J&K	Chdddangpa, Garra, Gujjar, Gaddi, etc.	12	NA
South			
Andhra Pradesh	Bhil, Chenchu, Gond, Kondas, Lambadis, Sugalis etc.	35	12
Kerala	Adiyam, Kammrar, Kondkappus, Malais, Palliyar, etc.	43	05
Tamilnadu	Irular, Kammara, Kondakapus, Kota, Toda etc.	36	06
Karnataka	Bhil, Chenchu, Goud, Kuruba, Koya, Mayaka, Toda,	50	02
Islands			
Andaman& Nicobar Islands	Jarawa, Nicobarese, Onges, Sentinelese, Shompens and Great Andamanese	06	05
Lakshadweep	Amindivi, Koyas, Malmis and Malacheries	0	NA

Source: Classified based on Annual Report, 2012-13. Ministry of Tribal Affairs.

Note: NA (Not Available): No PTGs are available in these states.

India is a vastly wealthy nation with a diverse population made up of many different ethnic groups. Of the 45,000 species of wild plants, 9,500 are significant from the perspective of ethnobotany. Of these, 7,500 species are used medicinally in traditional Native American medical practices. A total of 3,900 plant species are used by tribal people as food, including 145 species of roots and tubers, 521 species of leafy vegetables, 101 species of bulbs and flowers, 647 species of fruits, 525 species for fiber, 400 species for fodder, 300 species for the preparation and extraction of chemicals used as naturally occurring insecticides and pesticides, and 300 species for the extraction of gum, resins, dyes, and other materials.

Here the researcher divides the tribals into 4 categories in which they can become the backbone of India and also continue their existence in the Indian and Global markets.

Figure 1: types of tribal culture

Now, we get into more detail regarding tribal cultures.

Handicraft: Artisanry, crafting, and handcrafting are collective nouns for handicrafts. Handicraft involves manually preparing materials with hand tools. The outcomes can be functional or aesthetically pleasing. Natural, industrially produced, or possibly recycled resources were used to make the product. The product comes in vintage, updated traditional, or modern variants. A handicraft is any of a wide range of types of work where functional and decorative objects are entirely made by one's hand or by using only simple, non-automated related tools like scissors, carving implements, or hooks. This type of work is sometimes more specifically referred to as artisanal handicraft or handmade. It refers to a broad variety of imaginative and creative activities that are connected to creating things with one's hands and talent, including work with fabrics, moldable and stiff materials, paper, plant fibers, clay, etc. It is a traditional main sector of craft making.

Figure 1.1: handicraft

Handlooms: A loom called a "handloom" is one that weaves fabric devoid of power. Pit looms or frame looms are typically found in weavers' houses where hand weaving is done. Warp (length) and weft (width) are the two sets of yarn that are most commonly interlaced in weaving (width). The handloom industry is the second most important economic activity after agriculture in terms of creating jobs for people. Indian handlooms have an artistic and crafty component, which makes them a potential market for premium domestic and international consumers.

Figure 1.2: handlooms

Forest products: Any commodity obtained from forestry for commercial or direct use, such as lumber, paper, or pasture for cattle, is referred to as a forest product. Any commodity obtained from forestry for commercial or direct use, such as lumber, paper, or cattle feed, is referred to as a forest product. Wood, by far the most common

product of forests, is used for a variety of things, including fuel (in the form of firewood or charcoal), finished structural components for structures, and as a raw material for papermaking (in the form of wood pulp). Non-timber forest products are all other non-wood products made from forest resources, including a wide range of other forest products (NTFP). When forest products generate revenue for the neighborhood, they are perceived as having less of an adverse impact on the forest ecology. Timber, fuelwood, and several other non-wood goods are the main forest products. The wood-based companies that forest concessionaires have established will help people find work.

Figure 1.3: forest products

Fabrics: Fabric is a term used to describe a fabric or other materials created by weaving together threads such as cotton, nylon, wool, and silk. Fabrics are used to create items like clothing, drapes, and sheets. Fibers can be natural or synthetic, with polyester being the most widely used synthetic fiber and cotton being the most popular natural fiber. The characteristics of each type of fiber vary; some are strong and thick, while others are supple and flexible.

Figure 1.4: fabrics

Why do tribes congregate around specific brands? It's an intriguing question. Why should consumers initiate what would be a marketing action independently? The reason, as we've already seen, is that they don't approach it from a marketing perspective. Consumers create brand tribes for purely personal, non-marketing reasons. They do this because companies make it possible for them to establish personal connections and feel emotions.

Tribal development refers to the upliftment of the tribal community, which is at various stages of socioeconomic, cultural, and administrative realms of growth. This chapter will make an extensive effort to study the schemes, policies, and programs undertaken by the Government of India for the overall growth and development of the tribal community under the schemes of ITDP and ITDA in India and particularly in the State of Telangana. To ensure the progressive abolition of all forms of exploitation and a step towards the achievement of equality and social justice, it implies the social and economic development of the tribal people through time-bound, phased Integrated Tribal Development Programs/Agencies (ITDP/ITDA), and other programs suitable for the people's genius and economic situation. The goals of the tribal development policies are to start the overall growth of tribes so they can remain in civilization by interacting with others. Therefore, uniquely formulated policies, plan-wise allocations, sup-plan-wise allocations, forest policy, and other measures have been taken to provide the indigenous people special attention for their upliftment.

Literature Analysis

These are the text that describes the current research and various key findings in the related topic. Some of the research works and their key findings are mentioned below. Based on the review of the literature, the researcher can find the key factors which are responsible for the tribals in making them the pillar of India which are as follows:

Subramanyam,2003 The objective of the current study is to explore the educational system in the tribal villages through which the government tries to make effort on tribals where they try to learn about technology adaptation.

Mandavkar et al 2011, concluded their findings and said that tribal peoples now have some better job options, but for them to use these options effectively, they must increase their knowledge, ability, and efficiency. This could be accomplished by setting up programs like training, and demonstrations, and by giving the tribal people access to exhibits and contemporary tools and equipment. To provide tribal blocks with lucrative employment, the service and industrial sectors need to be expanded. The medium level of training requirements suggests that there is room to improve their knowledge and competence, which might be accomplished by giving them the confidence to take part in various programs. The training of tribal members about their jobs should receive increased focus from the extension organizations.

Kumar et al (2014) stated in their studies that Youth could be encouraged to start selling handmade goods the government should take steps to disseminate information about various programs, financing options, marketing support, and training so that people can compete with cheaper substitutes, especially those from China. This research paper explores if the government is trying to make the effort in the tribals and their product and also influence them about the training program.

Bhushan et al (2014) examine in their research paper Our nation is renowned as one of the top trade nations on the global scene, with a specialty in exporting a wide range of finished and semi-finished goods. One product that our nation exports to other nations throughout the world are handmade goods, which are likewise well-known and well-received elsewhere. Our community and culture are uniquely expressed via handicrafts. It produces foreign exchange revenues that are crucial for our economy's growth and improvement. Government should make encouragement and support available to maximize the discovery of this handcrafted business. The federal and state governments must move quickly to create new policies and channels for this environmentally beneficial sector, which requires little capital and yields great profits.

Verma et al, 2014 explain the importance of training for the tribals and also explore that most tribal males lack the basic agricultural knowledge, and factors including schooling, farming experience, aspirational level, cosmopolitanism, economic incentive, and propensity for innovation are related to tribal men's knowledge levels. The limitations mentioned included the lack of timely input availability, inadequate irrigation infrastructure, a lack of expertise, etc. as significant issues in farming. Various extension and training programs must effectively reach tribal men, and initiatives must be taken to promote gender-specific research to improve the content of extension messages that are suitable for farmers.

Thamminaina,2018 explore in their research paper that NGOs that have a thorough understanding of the community use a culturally sensitive strategy to effect the desired change. Such a strategy fosters relationships with trustworthy people. To inform the public about the anticipated effects of action is essential. NGOs send volunteers to live among potential beneficiaries and engage them in both formal and informal interactions. This makes them trustworthy and aids in the efficient execution of the projects. But none of the NGOs are successful. The way the initiatives are carried out is one of these NGOs' biggest weaknesses. It was discovered that the goals of the government organization force grassroots organizations to adopt short-term strategies without significant follow-up actions in the collaborative initiatives. However, the tribal members' acceptance of any program takes longer in communities. Currently, a large number of NGOs are functioning independently in the nation's tribal regions. They frequently spend limited resources very sparingly on comparable tasks. If they worked together based on shared interests, it would provide better results. A network of NGOs on both a national and global scale is required. An organization that streamlines NGOs' operations will be very effective. However, such an organization shouldn't eliminate any NGO's autonomy. Despite the flaws, there is no denying that NGOs serve as a safety net and are essential to the advancement of tribal communities. While they lack the magical abilities to instantly fix every issue, they can nonetheless serve as excellent development catalysts.

Sharma et al,2020 concluded in their study that Since ancient times, India has hosted a sizable portion of the global tribal population. In the context of India, the two states with the largest tribal populations are Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. Agriculture is the primary occupation of tribes. Despite enormous efforts, the tribal agricultural community still appears to be lacking in several necessities for enhanced agriculture and related areas. The current study aims to incorporate the varied training requirements of tribal farmers in the fields of crop production, animal husbandry, fisheries, poultry, goat rearing, and many other agricultural fields. Depending on the nature of their farming methods, tribal communities have different training demands. Despite several government and non-government programs and initiatives, tribal farmers continue to be underprivileged. Several initiatives have been taken to meet their training demands necessary continually to elevate them and bring them into the agricultural development's mainstream. Various program- and policy-based interventions may prove to be significant turning points in this regard.

Raju,2020 stated in his studies that the welfare systems are badly impacted by a variety of issues like Geographical and cultural isolation, a lack of adequate healthcare facilities, the inability to achieve food security, a lack of control over resources and properties, a lack of education and skills, malnutrition, inadequate access to clean drinking water, vulnerability to impact, crime, and violence are just a few of the factors that continue to disadvantage the citizens. These difficulties could make it difficult for them to make a living. In light of these issues, the government works to support the tribes through various welfare initiatives. This essay examines the socioeconomic situation of tribal populations and the programs put in place by the Telangana governments to aid tribal communities. Among other things, the Indian Constitution guarantees social and economic fairness, equality of status and opportunities, and the worth of every person. The Indian Constitution has been increasing with various provisions for calendar castes and calendar tribes to conserve and enhance their cultural, social, educational, and economic rights and to integrate these into the mainstream of India. Telangana's government makes significant efforts to enhance tribal living.

Agarwal et al,2020 explore the training importance and also stated that indigenous people are naturally skilled craftspeople. If their skills are developed, they may produce things that are in demand. If the proper training environment is provided, sustainable subsistence can be obtained. The training course should be comprehensive. Given their way of life, a program that considers that should be implemented. The training program should offer support up until self-sustainment when tribal people become knowledgeable in managing the entire supply chain of a product.

Yadav et al,2022 conclude in their studies that According to the current scenario, the government should support the handicraft industry to help migratory workers find local employment and participate in local economic activities in neighboring districts. Promote One District One Product (ODOP) and community startups as well to strengthen the rural economy. However, the ODOP industry has been negatively impacted by its frequent informality and lack of organization, as well as the additional barriers of inadequate institutional support, a lack of market knowledge, and a framework. Craftspeople in rural communities are capable of competing with the newest styles and trends. They merely need the appropriate support from the relevant authorities. India, according to Gandhi, was a country of villages, and if the rural women's and home-based business community shines, so will India get the strong pillar in front of the developed countries.

Objectives

- 1) To Suggest new strategies and ways to the development of tribal products in the Indian and Global Markets.
- 2) To Study the handicraft of India and ODOP on rural and tribal people of the handicraft sector.
- 3) To Study how training is beneficial in tribal Development.
- 4) To Identify the role of Government in the Development of tribes.

Research Methodology

Descriptive Research Design.

The secondary data source was used. The current investigation is supported by secondary information. In general, the necessary data was gathered from:

1. Books, Articles from Newspapers, Magazines, and Journals, Literature Analysis.
2. Various connected websites that deal directly or indirectly with themes linked to Indian Handloom, Tribals, and Make in India.

Discussion

Here the researcher discuss the strategies of marketing through which Government and Non-Government Organization help ingenious people for the marketing of their products

Existing Marketing Strategies or Existing Innovation Marketing Strategies

Tribal business owners in the community employed straightforward marketing strategies to promote and sell their woven handicrafts. These marketing campaigns targeted private, retail (wholesalers), and Government-owned retail chains using direct marketing techniques. Another type of direct marketing is the sale of goods through independently owned establishments in the village and one district.

Figure 2.0: marketing strategies

This conceptual diagram explains how tribals produce their goods, such as handicrafts, handlooms, and forest products, first. Then, the government trains them to make them perfect. Finally, the government and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) assist them in marketing their goods. Tribes prefer social media marketing to advertise their goods, and they also supply their goods to TERIFD outlets so that people from all over India can interact with indigenous people.

4 C's

After analyzing the literature review the researcher tries to find out the 4C's for through which tribals are facing the problem to market their products and the explanation is as follows:

The tribal business owners in the village who are engaged in the manufacturing and distribution of handcrafted goods, forest products, etc., encounter many challenges. Based on observational data and interview schedules, the problems and challenges experienced by entrepreneurs can be divided into the 4 C's.

Figure 3.0: figure of c's

Connectivity: The village is solely accessible by road. Getting to the village is difficult because of the bad road conditions and inadequate infrastructure. Since tourists are discouraged from visiting the caverns and other places of historical and religious significance, this harms the business of handloom goods, among other things.

Cost: As we all know that our Indian consumers believe in sales offers of low-cost products etc if they can buy the costly product they prefer the mall and showroom here they get the same product but at a different rate they can prefer it but they can't prefer government showroom and fairs. As cost is also a challenge for the handloom industry in the Indian context market.

Competition: There is competition between tribal products and brand items. For example, if we are talking about honey, the pure honey that comes from the forest is produced by the tribe, whereas the other brands make their honey and the customers prefer those brands.

Communication: Another issue or worry for rural business owners is a lack of marketing initiatives and direct customer contact to getting feedback. The absence of structured, contemporary management-based branding and positioning communication substantially hinders the marketing of hand-block printed handloom products.

The review of the aforementioned earlier literature has revealed that the most significant obstacle to the sale of tribal goods such as handicrafts, handlooms, and forest products in this issue. The tribal community has a marketing problem that has to be resolved, and the art-making process needs to be enhanced, according to the researcher's analysis of the literature. Governments and non-governmental organizations have made significant efforts, yet they continue to face the issues listed below, which were discovered through a literature analysis:

- a) Lack of Education.
- b) Lack of Brand Awareness
- c) Lack of Brand Image
- d) Lack of Brand Equity
- e) Lack of technology
- f) Lack of connectivity of tribal people with non-tribal people.

Suggestions

The government should take action to stop design copying. Registration of the design is required. The government ought to support the participation of artisans in fairs, exhibitions, and other events. In this regard, a coordinated effort must be done with a focus on the role and issues of artisans, government business sector policies, the

function of mediating organizations, especially non-governmental organizations, and sustainable markets. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the degree to which tribal people's livelihoods are safeguarded by the use of online platforms, media marketing techniques, and social networking websites that allow for interactivity and relationship-building. The purpose of the present is to make the most up-to-date tribal product marketing strategies known while also making sure that tribal people are given the best possible level of support. Customers can speak with a tribe directly once they sign up on these online channels. The contact may be more customized for users as compared to conventional strategies for combating marketing and advertising. Members of the tribe can benefit from the highest support price for their items without any agents interfering.

As well as being well known for its heritage and culture, India is also known for its tribal people, who share their culture with people in other nations, allowing those people to learn about Indian traditions and culture. Tribal people are also the foundation of India, so it is our responsibility to keep these sayings true.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the degree to which tribal people's livelihoods are safeguarded by the use of online platforms, media marketing techniques, and social networking websites that allow for interactivity and relationship-building. The purpose of the present is to make the most up-to-date tribal product marketing strategies known while also making sure that tribal people are given the best possible level of support. Customers can speak with a tribe directly once they sign up on these online channels. The contact may be more customized for users as compared to conventional strategies for combating marketing and advertising. Tribes can benefit from the highest support price for their items without any agents interfering. Considering the importance of with a focus on digital platforms, brand reputation, and global communication, this research project aims to investigate recent literature on the barriers to tribal marketing. This study looks into a range of problems that affect those who make handcrafted goods. The beauty and allure of its handiwork have always attracted a large number of tourists from both India and abroad. From simple materials, a skilled artisan may produce exquisite works of art.

Tribal handicrafts have made a significant contribution to the state and national economies in terms of employment and money generation, and they are significant components of our national heritage. The lack of sufficient information prevented planners and policymakers from coming up with a workable plan. There are some plans in place to promote native crafts. To create a database on tribal crafters, it is necessary to list tribal artisans, their craft-related activities, and the concentration of such handicraft pockets.

This study indicates that non-timber are the most significant influence has been played by forest products sustaining indigenous livelihoods and everyday needs in the region could aid in protecting and judiciously using the riches of the forest. however, Currently the tribal people are utilizing contemporary chances for the market, communication, and transportation also contemporary healthcare facilities, the conventional understanding of tribal customs and how to employ NTFPs in their pattern of employment could be useful in developing plans to protect the forest and environment.

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